

Measuring the Impacts of Fab Labs: A Review of Quantitative Research and Evidence

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Abstract

This review addresses a critical gap in academic research by systematically assessing the quantified societal impacts of Fab Labs. Recognizing the need for rigorous evidence to inform policy, funding, and strategic planning, it focuses on studies employing robust quantitative methodologies. Using the Fab City Full Stack as a framework, the review categorizes findings across seven interconnected layers, from local production technologies to global knowledge sharing. It evaluates measurable economic, educational, environmental, and social outcomes, emphasizing metrics derived from econometric models, longitudinal studies, and statistical analyses. By examining prior research methodologies, this study highlights the transformative potential of Fab Labs in fostering sustainable localized production, community empowerment, and educational innovation. The synthesis of empirical evidence provides actionable insights for stakeholders seeking to design evidence-driven interventions. Ultimately, this review strengthens the evidence base for Fab Labs' societal impact, supporting cities in their transition toward regenerative and inclusive ecosystems.

Keywords

Fab Labs, Fab City Full Stack, Impact Assessment, Empirical Evidence

1 Introduction

For over two decades, the global Fab Lab movement has championed open-access digital fabrication, with advocates claiming that Fab Labs and makerspaces foster innovation, democratize production, and stimulate local economies (Lindtner et al., 2016). However, the extent to which these claims are supported by empirical evidence remains unclear. This paper systematically reviews the available scientific literature to assess whether the societal impact of Fab Labs aligns with these high expectations.

A key initiative within this movement is the Fab City Global Initiative, launched in 2016 to promote urban self-sufficiency through localized, digitally enabled production (Moritz et al., 2024). Since its inception, the initiative has expanded to 40 cities and 14 regions worldwide (as of 2025), working toward the ambitious goal of producing everything they consume by 2054 (Diez, 2016). To operationalize this vision, the Fab City Full Stack framework (Diez et al., 2022) was introduced, outlining seven interconnected societal impact dimensions, called layers, to guide sustainable urban transformation.

Recognizing the need for systematic impact measurement, Fab City initiatives have begun developing metrics and assessment tools. These include the Fab City Data Dashboard, which standardizes impact reporting, the Global Working Group on Fab Labs and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (van der

Hijden et al., 2024), which creates SDG profiles for Fab Labs, and the Fab City Index (Boeing, 2024; Florentin et al., 2018), which aims to capture the current state of urban production on the path to self-sufficiency.

Given the interdisciplinary nature of Fab Lab research – spanning design, engineering, economics, and social sciences – this study employs an approach to map the extent, nature, and scope of existing research that relies on quantitative impact measurements. Rather than exclusively focusing on assessing the quality of empirical evidence for a particular impact, this review identifies key impact dimensions, challenges and research gaps across different methodologies and scientific disciplines (Munn et al., 2018).

By structuring findings within the Fab City Full Stack, this study not only synthesizes existing knowledge but also provides a practical framework for impact assessments. Our aim is to equip Fab Labs and Fab City initiatives with methodological tools to measure their success, generate quantitative evidence of their impact, and refine strategies for achieving long-term sustainability. By collecting and sharing empirical insights, this review supports Fab Labs and Fab Cities in conducting rigorous, evidence-based impact assessments and strengthening their role in local and global innovation ecosystems.

2 Background

2.1 Fab Labs and Fab Cities

A Fab Lab (fabrication laboratory) is a small-scale digital fabrication workshop equipped with tools such as 3D printers, laser cutters, and CNC machines, enabling individuals and communities to prototype and manufacture locally (Gershenfeld, 2007). Initially developed as a research lab at the MIT Center for Bits and Atoms, Fab Labs have since evolved into a global network, promoting open-source hardware, collaborative innovation, and local manufacturing (Gershenfeld et al., 2017; Menichinelli et al., 2017).

Fab Labs, makerspaces and similar open workshops and innovation labs are often credited with democratizing access to advanced manufacturing technologies, fostering STEM education, entrepreneurship, and social innovation (Hielscher, 2017; Smith et al., 2016; Walter-Herrmann & Büching, 2013). The underlying assumption is that open access to digital fabrication tools enables individuals to solve local problems, develop new businesses, and strengthen community resilience. However, empirical research on Fab Labs' long-term societal impact remains limited, and systematic evaluation frameworks are still emerging (Lowe et al., 2023).

The Fab City model extends the principles of Fab Labs to an urban scale, envisioning self-sufficient cities where production and recycling happen locally while knowledge and designs are shared globally (Buxbaum-Conradi, 2024; Diez, 2016). The approach aims to embed digital fabrication into urban ecosystems, linking makerspaces, universities, businesses, and policymakers to support sustainable local production. The aim of Fab Cities is the transition from the linear 'Product In, Trash Out' (PITO) production model to a 'Data In, Data Out' (DIDO) paradigm, where knowledge and designs are shared globally, but production and recycling occur locally – with Fab Cities pledging to be self-sustaining by 2054. By adopting this framework, cities can work towards greater resilience, sustainability, and community empowerment.

2.2 The Fab City Full Stack

In their introduction to the Fab City Full Stack, Diez et al. (2022) state that

“Fab Labs have been democratizing access to digital fabrication and building a global research and innovation network over the last two decades. However, they still face the challenge of creating an impact beyond individual realization through learning new technical skills and small-scale projects.”

The authors acknowledge the Fab City Global Initiative as the solution to this challenge, which “expands the purpose [of Fab Labs] to transforming society” and propose the Fab City Full Stack as a framework for defining and operationalizing each city’s own “Strategic Action Plan” to get from PITO to DIDO (ibid, 5).

The Fab City Full Stack aims to reduce the complexity of the systemic change required to get from PITO to DIDO by slicing it into seven interconnected layers.

- **Layer 1 Developing Infrastructure and Technologies for Local Production** refers e.g. to innovation spaces such as fab labs, technologies, machines, but also to the less tangible “building a sense of community around [spaces such as fab labs] with shared values” (ibid, 7).
- **Layer 2 Enabling New Forms of Learning** is concerned with a wide range of educational concepts and approaches, such as open educational resources, practice-based-learning or critical making, emerging from the fab city network and beyond.
- **Layer 3 Incubating Value-Generating Projects** tackles the challenge of turning designs into “projects that have economic, scientific, and social impact” (ibid, 8) both locally and globally.
- **Layer 4 Orchestrating Efforts between Local Communities and Initiatives** focuses on local ecosystems, i.e. actors and stakeholders from the public and private sector, academia and civil society.
- **Layer 5 Prototyping Place-Based Interventions** explores fab labs in fab cities as urban experimentation spaces where citizens, with public and private support, implement, test, and iterate innovative business opportunities and circular economy solutions. This layer also refers to creating open markets and guiding policymakers in scaling successful models.
- **Layer 6 Applying Bioregional Strategies** considers the natural ecosystems and cultural contexts of the regions in which fab cities are situated to develop strategies that harmonize human activities with the environment and calls for multi-species approaches to all interventions.
- **Layer 7 Sharing Knowledge with Global Networks** is concerned with the exchange of information and best practices between local and global communities to accelerate innovation and adaptation.

In summary, the Full Stack model articulates the ambitions and goals of Fab City initiatives. In this study, it serves as an analytical lens, providing a structured approach to systematising the societal impacts explored and measured in the reviewed scientific literature.

3 Methodology

A review of research literature on the impacts of Fab Labs was conducted following established guidelines for scoping reviews (Munn et al., 2018), including identifying the relevant literature, charting key concepts (here measured impacts), and categorizing findings to provide actionable insights. This approach ensures that research findings are both systematically mapped and translated into practical tools for stakeholders in the Fab Lab ecosystem. The methodological procedures include systematic search and selection processes, predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, structured data extraction, critical appraisal of methodological rigor, and synthesis of findings to identify patterns and gaps in research. The impact dimensions underlying the Full Stack model provided the framework for assessing the findings.

The review focused on peer-reviewed scientific studies that explicitly measure the societal impacts of makerspaces (including Fab Labs) using robust methodologies, including clear impact definitions, appropriate data collection, and controls for external influences. By organizing the results within the Fab City Full Stack framework, this study not only synthesises existing research but also provides practical guidance for Fab Labs to conduct rigorous, evidence-based impact assessments, systematically collect data, and compare local experiences to drive informed decision-making.

Figure 1: Methodological steps for literature survey

The literature survey followed a structured process (see Figure 1):

1. **Initial Literature Search:** The literature search was conducted using the Scopus database, which is one of the largest and most comprehensive repositories of peer-reviewed academic publications. Scopus provides extensive coverage of scientific literature across disciplines, making it a suitable source for a systematic literature review. The search query was designed to capture all relevant publications dealing with the impact of Fab Labs and similar spaces such as makerspaces or hackerspaces.¹ This broad approach resulted in an initial dataset of 996 documents, including journal articles and conference papers.
2. **Cleaning and Filtering:** To refine the dataset, it was checked for duplicate records (not found), and only articles published after 2002 (the year the first Fab Lab was established at MIT) were kept, reducing the total to 988 publications.
- **Impact Categorization:** The studies were categorised as to the type of impact measured. Each study was assigned to one or more of the seven layers of the Fab City Full Stack, depending on the impacts being mentioned in the study. We employed an automated text analysis using OpenAI’s natural language processing capabilities. Specifically, we used a Python-based implementation to classify studies based on their abstracts, ensuring a consistent and systematic assessment of their contributions.²
3. **Methodological Differentiation:** After impact categorisation, studies were assessed as to the methodological research approach to assess impacts, distinguishing between qualitative and quantitative methods. Again, OpenAI was employed to automatically classify the method used to assess the respective impacts. As a result, only 392 studies (approximately 40 % of the total) were found to quantitatively measure at least one of the analysed impacts and were therefore kept for further analysis.

¹ The query requires that both an impact term and a space term appear in any data field (title, abstract, or keywords) of the publication. See the Annex for details.

² Each abstract was analysed using a predefined prompt designed to instruct the GPT-4o model to assess its relevance to the study’s scope. For relevant abstracts, the model assigned one or more of the seven predefined Full Stack impact layers. To ensure consistency and reduce session variability, the model was configured with fixed parameters (e.g., zero temperature, structured output). An example of the prompt and configuration is provided in the annex.

4. **Shortlisting of Quantitative Studies:** To assess relevance and rigor of the remaining studies, each abstract was analysed with a layer-specific prompt designed to evaluate the clarity of the study's objectives, the alignment of the measured impact with the scope of the layer, the description of data sources and collection methods, and the validity of impact indicators. Only studies that fell within the scope of the layer and met the quality criteria were (hand-)selected by the author team for further analysis. In this way, the list of relevant studies was reduced to a manageable number of about 10 to 25 impact studies for each layer.³
5. **Critical Review and Synthesis of Shortlisted Studies:** Only the shortlist of relevant quantitative studies was critically reviewed, re-evaluated and summarized by the author team. For each layer, the studies were assessed based on the full paper regarding their content fit, quality and impact measurement results. If necessary, they were assigned to more fitting full-stack layers. For each layer, suitable studies were summarised according to the following criteria: What impacts are measured? What methods are used to measure these impacts? What empirical evidence is given?

Overall, the literature review reveals that only a small fraction of impact studies offers rigorous empirical assessments, underscoring the need for more systematic and standardized evaluation frameworks. However, existing empirical evidence does support the positive effects of Fab Labs and makerspaces, and a few high-quality studies stand out as models for improving future evidence collection.

4 Data

The initial literature search yielded approximately 1,000 research studies that deal with the societal impact of Fab Labs and other makerspaces. Of these contributions, nearly half were published in academic journals, while two-fifths appeared in conference proceedings. The remaining publications primarily consisted of book chapters.

The timeline of these studies shows a growing scientific interest in the topic. Notably, publications surged in the late 2010s, coinciding with and following the establishment of the Fab City Global Initiative. In 2014, during the 10th Fab Lab Conference in Barcelona, titled "From Fab Labs to Fab Cities", a public declaration was made to launch the Fab City Challenge. This initiative aimed to extend the principles of Fab Labs beyond individual makerspaces to entire cities and thus achieve a broader societal impact. After a peak in 2020, the number of published papers has stabilized, averaging around 100 per year (see Figure 2).

³ If the shortlist was still too long (in the case of layer 2 and layer 7), priority was given to the studies that were most frequently cited.

Figure 2: Publications histogram

An analysis of the leading academic journal outlets (Table 2 in the Annex) reveals that publications on the impacts of makerspaces are primarily concentrated in educational sciences, with a strong focus on engineering education (*Int. J. Engineering Education, Int. J. Technology and Design Education, Frontiers in Education, Int. J. STEM Education*) and digital learning (*Int. J. Child-Computer Interaction, Library Hi Tech, Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, Information and Learning Science, British Journal of Educational Technology, Educational Technology Research and Development*). Research and innovation (*R&D Management, Research Policy, Innovations*) and design (*Design Journal, Strategic Design Research Journal*) play a secondary role. Sustainability and foresight studies are marginal disciplines.

Consistent with this journal distribution, the automated categorisation of examined impacts (Figure 3) confirms that most studies address the educational dimension (Layer 2), followed by impacts on local ecosystems (Layer 4) and on innovation, creativity and entrepreneurship (Layer 3). In contrast, the remaining layers of the Fab City Full Stack receive significantly less attention. Particularly striking is the virtual absence of studies assessing the ecological impacts and (bio-)regional consequences (Layer 6).

Moreover, a significant proportion of the identified studies examine impacts primarily from a conceptual or qualitative case study perspective (light bar), without engaging in empirical measurements (dark bar). The differentiation between methodological approaches indicates that three-fifths of the studies do not incorporate any quantitative assessment of the examined impacts.

Figure 3: Impact dimensions examined, by methodological approach

The following analysis highlights the few studies that have rigorously measured impacts, offering both inspiration and practical examples for Fab Cities and cities worldwide seeking to embrace sustainable urban transformation through digital fabrication, circular economy principles, and knowledge sharing, while also demonstrating how to collect and utilize empirical evidence effectively.

5 Analysis

To ensure a structured and comprehensive analysis, this study evaluates quantitative research on Fab Lab impacts using a layered approach based on the Fab City Full Stack framework. Each layer represents a distinct impact dimension, spanning local production technologies to global knowledge sharing, where Fab Labs can play a significant role. By examining studies layer by layer, this approach provides an overview of the existing empirical evidence, highlighting key metrics, methodologies, and best practices used to measure societal, economic, environmental, and educational impacts of Fab Labs. Additionally, it allows for comparative insights, identifying gaps in research and showcasing effective methods that can guide future studies and policy decisions. A tabular overview of the studies split by layers is presented in the annex.

5.1 Impacting the accessibility of technologies and infrastructures

Level 1 focuses on the provision of physical and institutional infrastructure that supports Fab City initiatives and their potential social impact. The key goal at this level is to establish open-access spaces, such as Fab Labs, and provide the public with digital fabrication technologies and open-source product designs, making production and innovation more accessible in urban settings. However, the success of this effort depends not just on the local availability of these resources but on their actual use, especially by individuals who may not have had prior access to such technologies. Therefore, a crucial factor in assessing the social impact is determining how effectively these infrastructures reach underserved communities and provide them with meaningful opportunities for participation.

There is a notable lack of impact studies that assess the effects of Fab Labs or makerspaces on the participation and inclusion of specific communities. Social outcomes like inclusion and participation are

inherently complex and subjective, which makes them difficult to measure. These outcomes often rely on qualitative data, such as personal narratives, relationships, and community cohesion. One of the few studies addressing accessibility uses a multi-case study approach and introduces a maturity grid tool for cross-comparing performances (Corsini & Moultrie, 2020): the impact is operationalised by defining four performance levels regarding the “access (to tools, technology, and support)”. A compelling method for evaluating the accessibility of local production infrastructure involves analysing walking distance catchment areas for maker services (Menichinelli et al., 2024). This approach enables the measurement and comparison of maker infrastructure accessibility within Fab Cities by assessing the geographic areas and populations served.

5.2 Impacting skills and capabilities

Layer 2 explores how Fab Cities through access to local production technologies and infrastructures foster new forms of learning and empowerment. A key aspect of the social impact of Fab City initiatives is determining whether Fab Lab users develop new skills and capabilities through in these environments. Notably, this layer has been the focus of numerous quantitative impact studies, many of which examine the effects of makerspace experiences on children or engineering students.

All reviewed studies on Layer 2 consistently highlight the positive impact of makerspaces on their users and visitors. These effects are typically measured through indicators such as self-efficacy in various fields (Andrews et al., 2021; Hilton, Nagel, & Linsey, 2018; Hilton, Smith, et al., 2018; Hilton et al., 2020), academic achievements (Hilton, Nagel, & Linsey, 2018; Yin et al., 2020), technological awareness (Sinha et al., 2020), and motivation toward makerspaces or engineering in general (Carbonell et al., 2019). Makerspaces serve as valuable learning environments, equipping individuals with hands-on experience, fostering ingenuity, and enabling them to engage with cutting-edge technology. However, these studies do not compare this emerging learning model with traditional teaching approaches, leaving the relative effectiveness of makerspaces as a learning environment unassessed.

5.3 Impacting innovation and entrepreneurship

Layer 3 examines the role of Fab City initiatives in value creation, particularly through the development of new products and business models. Makerspaces are supposed to serve as innovation hubs by providing an environment conducive to creative experimentation and technological advancement. While existing studies document specific innovation activities within makerspaces (Geist et al., 2019; Kundu et al., 2019), empirical evidence on their broader, systemic impact remains limited.

Notably, a widely cited study of user surveys (Halbinger, 2018) finds that makerspace members exhibit a higher likelihood of developing and commercializing innovations compared to the general population. Similarly, survey data from a hardware maker community show that having access to makerspaces is linked to a higher likelihood of becoming a maker entrepreneur (Zhouxuan Li et al., 2022). Moreover, data from cross-sectional time series studies suggest that the presence of hackerspaces in a local area can boost digital entrepreneurship by supporting the creation of start-ups (Cuntz & Peuckert, 2023).

5.4 Impacting collaboration and local ecosystems

Layer 4 explores the role of Fab Cities in supporting local ecosystems. Fab Labs and makerspaces are supposed to help create dynamic innovation networks by fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing. They serve as bridges between formal institutions, such as universities and companies, and informal groups, including individual makers and hobbyists (Cohendet et al., 2021). While our literature survey identifies this layer as the second most frequently discussed impact dimension, it also has the lowest proportion of quantitative impact studies.

The key role of Fab Labs in orchestrating local stakeholders, in cultivating communities of practice and in enhancing civic engagement for urban development is documented by a number of qualitative case studies (Bravi et al., 2018; Fasoli & Tassinari, 2017; Galaleldin & Anis, 2017; Viseur et al., 2023), including

multiple-case comparisons (Menichinelli, 2020). Some of the reviewed studies, while using a quantitative approach, focus on the influence of various factors that shape collaboration within makerspaces rather than examining the direct impact of makerspaces on local ecosystems (Chng et al., 2022; Dúo-Terrón et al., 2022; Y. Li et al., 2023). A semi-quantitative survey approach shows a positive effect of corporate makerspaces on the collaboration of companies with external stakeholders (Rieken et al., 2024).

5.5 Impacting urban transformation

We found very few rigorous quantitative impact studies that address Layers 5 and 6, which are focused on place-based prototyping and bioregional strategies. One reason may be the diffuse and systemic nature of the impacts associated with these layers: transformative outcomes like community empowerment, peer learning, or cultural adaptation of circular practices are harder to isolate and less amenable to standard economic proxies like productivity or start-up success. As a result, they are often better explored through qualitative, design-based, or participatory methods.

Both Layers 5 and 6 are highly context-specific, typically involving multiple stakeholders and long-term, often emergent outcomes. Effectively measuring their impact would require complex, longitudinal, and systems-oriented approaches that are rarely applied in small-scale maker contexts. While collaborations with municipal or regional governments could enable such studies, reproducibility remains a challenge since most of these projects are one-off and locally embedded.

Layer 6 presents additional methodological challenges. Fab Labs, which often experiment with circular and regenerative practices, frequently lack the capacity for environmental accounting. The impacts of these initiatives unfold over time and extend beyond the immediate confines of the lab, making attribution difficult. For example, a successful circular design workshop might inspire more sustainable behaviours, but this does not necessarily translate into measurable environmental benefits. Essentially, the connection between output and impact is not always as direct or quantifiable, as demonstrated in the exceptional case of material and time saving bike repairs (Singh, 2022).

5.6 Impacting global knowledge diffusion

Layer 7 focusses on the role of Fab Cities in the global exchange of knowledge. Measuring the impact of makerspaces on the global diffusion of knowledge presents significant challenges due to the intangible and asynchronous nature of knowledge transfer. Open-source designs can be disseminated, reused, and modified worldwide without clear or publicly available metrics to track their diffusion. Key platforms like GitHub and Wikifactory host valuable data, yet access for researchers is limited, and conventional indicators such as downloads or forks are often incomplete or unavailable.

Alternative data sources, such as participant lists and surveys from international maker events (like FABx, GOSH, or GIG) offer potential insights into global knowledge exchange networks. Additionally, publicly funded projects generate relevant quantitative data, but much of it remains unpublished in reports, dashboards, or grey literature, making it inaccessible for systematic analysis. These challenges underscore the need for stronger collaboration between researchers and practitioners to identify, extract, and translate existing data into formats suitable for academic study, thereby enabling a more rigorous assessment of makerspaces' role in global knowledge diffusion.

None of the reviewed studies directly measure the impact of Fab Labs or makerspaces on the global diffusion of knowledge. However, they consistently highlight the role of sharing maker crafts and open-source designs through online platforms, as well as interactions within the global maker network, as key factors influencing knowledge transfer, acquisition, and innovation (Zhenhua Li & Gao, 2021; Ogunjemilua et al., 2020; Tseng & Resnick, 2016).

6 Practical implications and conclusion

This review analysed quantitative impact studies that have been published over the last 25 years using the Fab City Full Stack framework, revealing strong evidence in some impact areas and significant gaps in others. The most consistently studied dimension is Layer 2 (skills and learning), with multiple studies demonstrating positive effects on self-efficacy, STEM interest, and academic achievement. Layer 3 (innovation and entrepreneurship) also shows promising results, linking makerspace access with increased likelihood of venture creation and innovation diffusion. In contrast, Layers 5, 6, and 7 (place-based interventions, bioregional strategies, and global knowledge sharing) are rarely addressed using quantitative methods, despite their importance for the Fab City vision. This uneven distribution suggests that the most transformative and systemic impacts of Fab Labs are also the least empirically examined.

A major reason for this gap lies in the methodological focus on individual-level outcomes such as skill acquisition, self-efficacy, or entrepreneurial activity. These are easier to capture through surveys, pre/post-tests, and other methods, and thus dominate the evidence base. However, this narrow focus risks overlooking the broader ambitions of Fab Labs: enabling urban resilience, democratizing production, and supporting regenerative local economies.

The systemic effects envisioned in the Full Stack are not beyond measurement. They require creative, context-sensitive approaches capable of capturing dynamic, long-term, and networked change. Participatory evaluation, geospatial analysis, and longitudinal mixed-methods research are promising directions.

To advance both research and practice, two key shifts are needed: First, impact assessment must evolve from static evaluation toward methodological pluralism. Mixed approaches can reveal how different Full Stack layers interact, e.g., how local access to technology might foster skills, which in turn enable innovation or community engagement. Second, assessments must serve learning, not just accountability. Fab Cities would benefit from modular, self-directed impact tools that prioritize reflection, iteration, and relevance to local priorities. These tools should include indicators that address distributional effects, asking not only what changes but also for whom.

For policymakers, the current evidence base supports investment in Fab Labs as enablers of inclusive innovation, particularly in education and early-stage entrepreneurship. However, funding models must move beyond infrastructure to support programming, collaboration, and long-term engagement. Impact research can help justify support for experimental, open-ended spaces that may not fit conventional innovation metrics but generate significant public value.

Future research should prioritize three goals. First, connect the layers to understand how impacts propagate across domains rather than in isolation. Second, measure the intangible by developing proxies and composite indicators for social cohesion, knowledge flows, or empowerment. Third, co-create research frameworks with Fab Lab communities to ensure legitimacy, usability, and contextual relevance.

Fab Labs are more than technical environments. They are social infrastructures with the capacity to anchor new ways of producing, learning, and belonging. Realizing this potential requires a shift in how we understand and assess impact, from isolated metrics to interconnected insights, from external auditing to internal agency. The Fab City Full Stack offers a useful foundation. Transforming it into a participatory, modular toolkit could help cities and labs not only measure change but shape it.

AI Disclosure Statement

As detailed in this manuscript, large language models (LLMs) were employed in this study to assist with the classification and synthesis of the literature. Additionally, AI-assisted tools were utilized to refine the structure and clarity of the manuscript. The authors carefully reviewed and edited all AI-generated content and take full responsibility for the final version of this publication.

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Annex

Tables of Analysis

Table 1: Selected studies of the impact on accessibility of technologies and infrastructure (Layer 1)

Study	Relevant Impact	Data	Analytical method	Evidence
Corsini and Moultrie (2020)	impact of humanitarian makerspaces on crisis-affected populations	in-field observations, interviews with beneficiaries and employees, workshop with employees	multi-case study approach, maturity grid tool, cross-comparison, triangulation	The study shows how makerspaces support design activities among migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers.
Menichinelli et al. (2024)	accessibility of maker services	15-minute walking distance catchment areas of maker services	analysis of geographic accessibility	Barcelona performs better in terms of reached area and population than Milano.

Table 2: Selected studies of the impacts on skills and attitudes (Layer 2)

Study	Relevant Impact	Data	Analytical method	Evidence
Hilton, Nagel, and Linsey (2018)	effect of makerspace involvement on academic achievement	survey of self-efficacy and makerspace involvement with GPA data for academic achievement	two-way correlation analysis between makerspace involvement and GPA	Students who are involved in makerspace show higher academic achievements.
Sinha et al. (2020)	impact of a mobile makerspace on the awareness and engagement in 3D printing and STEAM education	self-reported surveys on familiarity, attitude, interest, and self-efficacy as well as observations of participant distribution and engagement	statistical analysis of pre- and post-exposure survey results, along with qualitative observations of participant engagement	Participation increases awareness of 3D printing technology, indicating the effectiveness in bridging gaps among students with varying initial familiarity.
Yin et al. (2020)	impact on students' computational thinking skills and dispositions	CT integrated achievement tests and self-reported surveys	paired t-tests and (multivariate) analysis of covariance	Maker activities affect computational thinking skills and dispositions of students.

Table 3: Selected studies of the impacts on innovation and entrepreneurship (Layer 3)

Study	Relevant Impact	Data	Analytical method	Evidence
Cuntz and Peuckert (2023)	impact of hackerspaces on the local foundation rate of digital start-ups	hackerspaces registry, number of digital start-ups and other regional statistics	cross-sectional time series regression	The longer a local hackerspace exists, the higher is the rate of digital entrepreneurship, particularly in urban contexts.
Halbinger (2018)	impact on innovation and diffusion rates among makerspace participants.	survey of 558 participants from makerspaces worldwide.	comparison of makerspace survey to national innovation data	The rates of innovation and diffusion among makerspace participants are higher than in the general population.
Zhouxuan Li et al. (2022)	impact on the likelihood of a maker starting a new venture	survey of the hardware community Hackster IO	cross-sectional logit regression	Access to makerspaces fosters the creation of maker-founded firms.

Table 4: Selected studies of the impacts on collaboration and local ecosystems (Layer 4)

Study	Relevant Impact	Data	Analytical method	Evidence
Menichinelli (2020)	contribution to local innovation ecosystems and urban transformation	data on European maker initiatives, events, platforms	multi-case study, structured comparative mapping	The study is largely conceptual and not quantitatively rigorous.
Rieken et al. (2024)	effect of corporate makerspaces on collaboration with external stakeholders	semi-quantitative survey of 22 managers and users		Corporate makerspaces increase collaboration of companies with external stakeholders.

Table 5: Selected study of the impacts on urban transformation (Layer 5 and 6)

Study	Relevant Impact	Data	Analytical method	Evidence
Singh (2022)	social, environmental, and economic benefits of DIY bike repair spaces in Switzerland and Sweden.	mixed data: semi-structured interviews, surveys, participant observation	qualitative coding + quantitative analysis of time and material use, linked to environmental indicators.	Makerspaces reduce material throughput and foster social cohesion; quantifiable impact via time savings and reuse metrics.

Table 6: Selected studies of the impacts on global knowledge diffusion (Layer 7)

Study	Relevant Impact	Data	Analytical method	Evidence
Tseng and Resnick (2016)	How online platforms enable sharing of maker knowledge	data from 426 projects, interviews with 11 users	content analysis, thematic coding of interviews	The study highlights design sharing as a form of global knowledge flow.
Ogunjemilua et al. (2020)	How makerspaces contribute to innovation via knowledge-sharing dynamics.	survey of 140 makerspace users across five Nigerian institutions.	descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis.	Makerspaces are local-global knowledge bridges: external communities and global knowledge sources are critical for innovation.
Zhenhua Li and Gao (2021)	Impact of social network embeddedness and openness in makerspaces on knowledge acquisition.	survey of 148 makers in China on external collaboration and interactions	Structural Equation Modelling	Interpersonal and institutional relationships, especially open knowledge-sharing structures, significantly impact innovation.

Scopus Search

For the Scopus search, we use the Python library *pybliometrics* with the following query:

```
query = f' TITLE-ABS-KEY ( fablab* OR "fab lab*" OR "maker space*" OR makerspace* OR hackerspace* OR hackspace* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( impact* OR effect* OR role* OR contribution* OR mechanism* ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "local development" ) AND PUBYEAR > 1999'
```

Table 7: Academic journals publishing on the topic

Nr. of Articles	Academic Journal	SJR 2023
16	International Journal of Engineering Education	0.350 (Q2)
14	International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction	1.142 (Q1)
11	Library Hi Tech	0.692 (Q1)
10	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction	0.979 (Q1)
9	Information and Learning Science	0.934 (Q1)
9	Sustainability (Switzerland)	0.672 (Q1)
7	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	3.118 (Q1)
7	International Journal of Technology and Design Education	0.812 (Q1)
7	Design Journal	0.351 (Q2)
6	British Journal of Educational Technology	2.425 (Q1)
6	R&D Management	1.756 (Q1)
6	Frontiers in Education	0.627 (Q2)
6	Strategic Design Research Journal	0.183 (Q2)
5	Educational Technology Research and Development	1.706 (Q1)
5	Journal of Science Education and Technology	1.595 (Q1)
5	Innovations	0.193 (Q4)
4	Research Policy	3.219 (Q1)
4	International Journal of STEM Education	2.035 (Q1)
4	Library Hi Tech News	0.385 (Q2)

Classification of Abstracts

To ensure a consistent data format, we used the *Pydantic* library in combination with OpenAI's Structured Output feature.

```
from pydantic import BaseModel
```

```
class StudyClassification(BaseModel):  
  
    # relevant scope:  
    impact_study: bool  
  
    # impact_dimensions:  
    layer1: bool  
    layer2: bool  
    layer3: bool  
    layer4: bool  
    layer5: bool  
    layer6: bool  
    layer7: bool  
  
    # methodological_approach:  
    qualitative_approach: bool  
    quantitative_approach: bool
```

In its simplest form, the prompt first asks the model to verify whether the study falls within the relevant scope, then to identify the impact dimensions addressed, and finally to distinguish between qualitative and quantitative approaches:

```
def build_prompt(abstract):  
    return f"""  
Classify the following scientific abstract according to these criteria:  
  
1 General Topic: Does the study address the impact of fablabs or similar makerspaces?  
Respond with a Boolean value.  
  
If true:  
  
2 Impact Dimensions: List all relevant impact dimensions from the following list:  
- Layer 1 - Developing Infrastructure and Technologies for Local Production  
- Layer 2 - Enabling New Forms of Learning  
- Layer 3 - Incubating Value-Generating Projects  
- Layer 4 - Orchestrating Efforts between Local Communities and Initiatives  
- Layer 5 - Prototyping Place-Based Interventions  
- Layer 6 - Applying Bioregional Strategies  
- Layer 7 - Sharing Knowledge with Global Networks  
Respond to each Layer with a Boolean value.  
  
3 Methodological Approach:  
- "1 - Qualitative / Case Study / Conceptual"  
- "2 - Quantitative Impact Measurement"  
Respond to each approach with a boolean value.  
  
Abstract to classify:  
\"\"\"  
{abstract}  
\"\"\"  
"""
```

The classification function employs the GPT-4o model with zero temperature, ensuring deterministic outputs, and restricts responses to align with our predefined schema:

```
def classify_study(abstract):  
  
    response = client.responses.parse(  
        model="gpt-4o",  
        temperature=0,  
        input=[
```

```

        {"role": "system", "content": "You are a classification assistant."},
        {"role": "user", "content": build_prompt(abstract)}
    ],
    text_format=StudyClassification
)

return response.output_parsed
    
```

Table 8: Classification Results

Full-Stack Layer	Number of classifications (quantitative / qualitative)					
	Classification method A: 1) layers per study 2) approach per study		Classification method B: 1) impact dimensions 2) approach per study		Classification method C: 1) impacts 2) approach per impact	
Layer 1	20	111	46	212	76	120
Layer 2	132	491	140	592	260	395
Layer 3	34	138	55	231	165	186
Layer 4	15	146	19	177	138	314
Layer 5	8	70	4	39	42	72
Layer 6	0	3	19	56	17	30
Layer 7	25	142	11	156	39	83

Shortlists

Impact dimension	Studies shortlisted for in depth analysis
<i>Technology and Infrastructure</i>	<p>Corsini & Moultrie (2020): Humanitarian makerspaces in crisis-affected communities. 10.1017/S0890060420000098.</p> <p>Kundu et al. (2019): Precision Vascular Delivery of Agrochemicals with Micromilled Microneedles (μMMNs). 10.1038/s41598-019-50386-8.</p> <p>Menichinelli et al. (2024): Assessing the impact of maker services in Barcelona and Milan towards the 15-minute city model through their accessibility. 10.1080/14606925.2024.2405773.</p> <p>Mewes & Sujesty (2019): The Application of a Solar Parabolic Trough Collector for the Melting of Plastic Waste. 10.1007/978-3-030-10856-4_17</p> <p>Ravindran et al. (2019): Open Source Waste Plastic Granulator. 10.3390/technologies7040074.</p> <p>Rieken et al. (2024): Corporate Makerspaces: An Empirical Mixed-Method Study of Its Elements and Their Impact on Users and Companies. 10.1080/10429247.2023.2295716.</p> <p>Wand et al. (2023): Satisfaction with maker space in central Guangzhou City: A survey of entrepreneurs. 10.18306/dlkxjz.2023.12.006</p>
<i>Skills and Capabilities</i>	<p>Abdurrahman (2019): Developing STEM Learning Makerspace for Fostering Student's 21st Century Skills in The Fourth Industrial Revolution Era. 10.1088/1742-6596/1155/1/012002.</p> <p>Andrews et al. (2021): Self-efficacy and belonging. the impact of a university makerspace. 10.1186/s40594-021-00285-0.</p> <p>Born et al. (2018): How Public Libraries are Keeping Pace with the Times: Core Services of Libraries in Informational World Cities. 10.1515/libri-2017-0029.</p> <p>Carbonell et al. (2019): Innovation, design, and self-efficacy: The impact of makerspaces. eid: 2-s2.0-85078791060.</p> <p>Chen & Cao (2022): Promoting maker-centred instruction through virtual professional development activities for K-12 teachers in low-income rural areas. 10.1111/bjet.13183.</p> <p>Eckhardt et al. (2021): Gender in the making: An empirical approach to understand gender relations in the maker movement. 10.1016/j.ijhcs.2020.102548.</p> <p>Halbinger (2018): The role of makerspaces in supporting consumer innovation and diffusion: An empirical analysis. 10.1016/j.respol.2018.07.008.</p> <p>Hilton et al. (2018): Investigating why students choose to become involved in a university makerspace through a mixed-methods study. eid: 2-s2.0-85051169333.</p> <p>Huang-Saad et al. (2016): Unpacking the impact of engineering entrepreneurship education that leverages the Lean LaunchPad Curriculum. 10.1109/FIE.2016.7757373.</p> <p>Jensen et al. (2016): State of the Art of Makerspaces - Success Criteria When Designing Makerspaces for Norwegian Industrial Companies. 10.1016/j.procir.2016.05.069.</p> <p>Lanci et al. (2018): Developing a measure of engineering students' makerspace learning, perceptions, and interactions. eid: 2-s2.0-85051174279.</p> <p>Longo et al. (2017): University makerspaces: Characteristics and impact on student success in engineering and engineering technology education. eid: 2-s2.0-85030533455.</p> <p>Max et al. (2022): The relationship between self-assessment and performance in learning TPACK : Are self-assessments a good way to support preservice teachers' learning? 10.1111/jcal.12674.</p> <p>Morocz et al. (2016): Relating student participation in university maker spaces to their engineering design self-efficacy. eid: 2-s2.0-84983341689.</p> <p>Radniecki, (2017): Supporting 3D modeling in the academic library. 0.1108/LHT-11-2016-0121.</p> <p>Saorín et al. (2017): Makerspace teaching-learning environment to enhance creative competence in engineering students. 10.1016/j.tsc.2017.01.004.</p> <p>Selznick et al. (2022): Equitably Linking Integrative Learning and Students' Innovation Capacities. 10.1007/s10755-021-09570-w.</p>

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	<p>Sinha et al. (2020): The Impact of a Mobile 3D Printing and Making Platform on Student Awareness and Engagement. 10.3390/ejihpe12080071</p> <p>Stevenson et al. (2019): By design: Professional learning ecologies to develop primary school teachers' makerspaces pedagogical capabilities. 10.1111/bjet.12743.</p> <p>Vongkulluksn et al. (2018): Motivational factors in makerspaces: a mixed methods study of elementary school students' situational interest, self-efficacy, and achievement emotions. 10.1186/s40594-018-0129-0.</p> <p>Wang et al. (2022): Entrepreneurship education enhances entrepreneurial creativity: The mediating role of entrepreneurial inspiration. 10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100570.</p>
<p><i>Innovation and entrepreneurship</i></p>	<p>Abdurrahman (2019): Developing STEM Learning Makerspace for Fostering Student's 21st Century Skills in The Fourth Industrial Revolution Era. 10.1088/1742-6596/1155/1/012002.</p> <p>Andrews et al. (2021): Self-efficacy and belonging. the impact of a university makerspace. 10.1186/s40594-021-00285-0.</p> <p>Carbonell et al. (2019): Innovation, design, and self-efficacy: The impact of makerspaces. eid: 2-s2.0-85078791060.</p> <p>Chen & Cao (2022): Promoting maker-centred instruction through virtual professional development activities for K-12 teachers in low-income rural areas. 10.1111/bjet.13183.</p> <p>Cuntz & Peuckert (2023): From hackers to start-ups: Innovation commons and local entrepreneurial activity. 10.1016/j.respol.2022.104675.</p> <p>Do-Terrn et al. (2022): Impact of the Pandemic on STEAM Disciplines in the Sixth Grade of Primary Education. 10.3390/ejihpe12080071.</p> <p>Geist et al. (2019): Clinical Immersion: An Approach for Fostering Cross-disciplinary Communication and Innovation in Nursing and Engineering Students. DOI: 10.1097/NNE.0000000000000547.</p> <p>Halbinger (2018): The role of makerspaces in supporting consumer innovation and diffusion: An empirical analysis. 10.1016/j.respol.2018.07.008.</p> <p>Hilton et al. (2018): Investigating why students choose to become involved in a university makerspace through a mixed-methods study. eid: 2-s2.0-85051169333</p> <p>Hilton et al. (2018): Makerspace Involvement and Academic Success in Mechanical Engineering. 10.1109/FIE.2018.8658875</p> <p>Hilton et al. (2018): University Makerspaces: More Than Just Toys. 10.1115/DETC2018-86311.</p> <p>Hilton et al. (2020): Report on Engineering Design Self-Efficacy and Demographics of Makerspace Participants Across Three Universities. 10.1115/1.4046649.</p> <p>Huang-Saad et al. (2016): Unpacking the impact of engineering entrepreneurship education that leverages the Lean LaunchPad Curriculum. 10.1109/FIE.2016.7757373.</p> <p>Kundu et al. (2019): Precision Vascular Delivery of Agrochemicals with Micromilled Microneedles (μMMNs). 10.1038/s41598-019-50386-8.</p> <p>Stevenson et al. (2019): By design: Professional learning ecologies to develop primary school teachers' makerspaces pedagogical capabilities. 10.1111/bjet.12743.</p> <p>Wang et al. (2022): Entrepreneurship education enhances entrepreneurial creativity: The mediating role of entrepreneurial inspiration. 10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100570.</p> <p>Yin et al. (2020): Improving and Assessing Computational Thinking in Maker Activities. the Integration with Physics and Engineering Learning. 10.1007/s10956-019-09794-8.</p> <p>Sinha et al. (2020): The Impact of a Mobile 3D Printing and Making Platform on Student Awareness and Engagement. 10.3390/ejihpe12080071.</p>
<p><i>Collaboration and local ecosystems</i></p>	<p>Bao (2025): Do makerspaces affect entrepreneurship? If so, who, how, and when? 10.1002/smj.3664.</p> <p>Bravi et al. (2018): Manufacturing labs: where new digital technologies help improve life quality. 10.18421/IJQR12.04-11.</p> <p>Chng et al. (2022): Toward capturing divergent collaboration in makerspaces using motion sensors. 10.1108/ILS-08-2020-0182.</p>

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	<p>Corsini & Moultrie (2020): Humanitarian makerspaces in crisis-affected communities. 10.1017/S0890060420000098.</p> <p>Fasoli & Tassinari (2017): Engaged by Design: The Role of Emerging Collaborative Infrastructures for Social Development. 10.1080/14606925.2017.1352819.</p> <p>Galaleldin et al. (2017): Impact of makerspaces on cultivating students' communities of practice. eid: 2-s2.0-85030549277</p> <p>Grahame et al. (2019): Community engagement and service-learning: Putting faces to a community to create better engineers. eid: 2-s2.0-85078735780</p> <p>Halbinger (2018): The role of makerspaces in supporting consumer innovation and diffusion: An empirical analysis. 10.1016/j.respol.2018.07.008.</p> <p>Higgins et al. (2023): Investigating an Equity-based Participatory Approach to Technology-rich Learning in Community Recreation Centers. 10.1145/3544548.3581567.</p> <p>Hicks & Faulk (2018): Do entrepreneur-focused facility incentives create economic impacts? Evidence from Indiana. 10.1108/JEPP-D-18-00013.</p> <p>Li et al. (2023): The impact of government subsidies on the human resources and innovation output of makerspaces according to signal theory. 10.1504/IJTM.2023.10053921.</p> <p>Menichinelli (2020): Exploring the impact of Maker initiatives on cities and regions with a research through design approach. 10.4013/SDRJ.2020.131.07.</p> <p>Monaco & Herce (2023): Impact of Maker Movement on the Urban Resilience Development: Assessment Methodology and Analysis of EU Research and Innovation Projects. 10.3390/su151712856.</p> <p>Rieken et al. (2024): Corporate Makerspaces: An Empirical Mixed-Method Study of Its Elements and Their Impact on Users and Companies. 10.1080/10429247.2023.2295716.</p> <p>Singh (2022): The Sustainability Potential of Upcycling. 10.3390/su14105989.</p> <p>Viseur (2023): How makers responded to the Personal Protective Equipment shortage during the COVID-19 pandemic: An analysis focused on the Hauts-de-France region. 10.1016/j.emj.2023.04.014.</p> <p>Wei (2022): Incubation model of the Maker Spaces in China: co-working or co-creating? 10.1080/09537325.2021.1916455.</p>
<p><i>Urban transformation</i></p>	<p>Bravi et al. (2018): manufacturing labs: where new digital technologies help improve life quality. 10.18421/IJQR12.04-11.</p> <p>Menichinelli (2020): Exploring the impact of Maker initiatives on cities and regions with a research through design approach. 10.4013/SDRJ.2020.131.07.</p> <p>Monaco & Herce (2023): Impact of Maker Movement on the Urban Resilience Development: Assessment Methodology and Analysis of EU Research and Innovation Projects. 10.3390/su151712856.</p> <p>Ravindran et al. (2019): Open Source Waste Plastic Granulator. 10.3390/technologies7040074.</p> <p>Singh (2022): The Sustainability Potential of Upcycling. 10.3390/su14105989.</p>
<p><i>Global knowledge diffusion</i></p>	<p>Halbinger (2018): The role of makerspaces in supporting consumer innovation and diffusion: An empirical analysis. 10.1016/j.respol.2018.07.008.</p> <p>Li & Gao, Xuan (2021): Makers' relationship network, knowledge acquisition and innovation performance: An empirical analysis from China. 10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101684.</p> <p>Li et al. (2022): Institutions and Maker Entrepreneurship. eid: 2-s2.0-85152233053.</p> <p>Ogunjemilua et al. (2020): The Nexus of Knowledge Sharing and Innovations in the Informal Sector: The Case of Otigba Hardware Cluster in Nigeria. 10.1007/978-3-030-27285-2_9.</p> <p>Rieken et al. (2024): Corporate Makerspaces: An Empirical Mixed-Method Study of Its Elements and Their Impact on Users and Companies. 10.1080/10429247.2023.2295716.</p> <p>Tseng & Resnick (2016): Spin: Examining the role of engagement, integration, and modularity in supporting youth creating documentation. 10.1145/2901790.2901868.</p>

	<p>Viseur et al. (2023): How makers responded to the Personal Protective Equipment shortage during the COVID-19 pandemic: An analysis focused on the Hauts-de-France region. DOI: 10.1016/j.emj.2023.04.014.</p> <p>Yang et al. (2025): More is better? Investigating the influence of the characteristics of training activity participation on maker innovation performance. 10.1108/EJIM-11-2022-0659.</p>
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